

DRYAD

Demonstration and modelling of Nature-based solutions to enhance the resilience of Mediterranean agro-silvo-pastoral ecosystems and landscapes

The project

DRYAD, a Horizon Europe project running from **2024 to 2028**, will contribute to the **Mission Adaptation to Climate Change** by developing and implementing **real-life, climate-resilient nature-based solutions for Mediterranean agro-silvo-pastoral ecosystems**.

The project integrates **cutting-edge scientific, technological, social, and business innovations** with transformative solutions, supporting a multi-level, cross-sectoral, integrated, and adaptive management governance through the **development of Decision Support Systems**.

Demonstration and replication regions

The proposal will be centered around **development, testing and demonstrating nature-based solutions** in 5 Demonstration Regions (DRs) and will be transferred to 3 Replication Regions (RRs).

Consortium

The project includes **27 partners** from **6 European countries** (Spain, Netherlands, Portugal, Italy, Greece, France)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No GA 101156076

Funded by the European Union